

TORSION OF CLOSED SECTION, ORTHOTROPIC THIN-WALLED BEAMS

Anikó Pluzsik, Ákos Sapkás and László P. Kollár

*Department of Mechanics, Materials and Structures, Budapest University of Technology and
Economics 1521 Hungary, Műegyetem rkpt. 1.
Tel.: +36 1 463-2315, Fax: +36 1 463-1773, e-mail: lkollar@eik.bme.hu*

SUMMARY: The paper presents a theory for thin-walled closed section orthotropic beams, which takes into account the shear deformation in restrained warping induced torque. First we gave the analytical “exact” solution assuming independent warping functions for each wall-segment. We presented the solution of this governing equation system for simply supported beams subjected to sinusoidal load. Then (for our simplified beam theory) we gave replacement stiffnesses, which are independent of the length of the beam. The effect of restrained warping and shear deformation was investigated through numerical examples.

KEYWORDS: closed section, beam theory, torsion, restrained warping, shear deformation

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastic (composite), thin-walled beams are widely used in the aerospace industry and are increasingly applied in the infrastructure. Thin-walled beams are often made with closed cross sections because of their high torsional stiffness.

Classical beam theories, which neglect bending-torsion coupling, transverse shear deformation and torsional warping stiffness often fail to predict the behavior of closed section composite beams. To avoid the undesirable bending-torsion coupling, beams are often manufactured such that their layup is orthotropic [2]. However, the effect of restrained warping may not be neglected. This is illustrated in Fig. 1. The classical beam theory assumes that the cross sections remain plane (left), however cross sections of composite beams may warp significantly (right).

These beam theories, also included in classical textbooks [8], calculate the bimoment (\hat{M}_ω) and the Saint Venant torque (\hat{T}_{sv}) as

$$\hat{M}_\omega = \overline{EI}_\omega \Gamma, \quad \hat{T}_{sv} = \overline{GI}_t \vartheta, \quad (1)$$

where \overline{EI}_ω is the warping stiffness, \overline{GI}_t is the torsional stiffness.

Fig. 1: Plane cross section (left), and warped cross section (right)

ϑ is the rate of twist (which is the first derivative of the rotation of the cross section $\vartheta = d\psi / dx$), and

$$\Gamma = -\frac{d\vartheta}{dx}, \quad (2)$$

where x is the axial coordinate.

The torque (\hat{T}) is the sum of the Saint-Venant torque (\hat{T}_{sv}) and the restrained warping induced torque (\hat{T}_ω)

$$\hat{T} = \hat{T}_{sv} + \hat{T}_\omega, \quad (3)$$

where the latter is calculated as

$$\hat{T}_\omega = -\frac{d\hat{M}_\omega}{dx}. \quad (4)$$

Eqns. 1-4 give the well-known equation

$$\hat{T} = \overline{GI}_t \vartheta - \overline{EI}_\omega \frac{d^2\vartheta}{dx^2}. \quad (5)$$

In the theory, presented in this paper, we assume [9] that the rate of twist ϑ consists of two parts

$$\vartheta = \vartheta_B + \vartheta_S, \quad (6)$$

where subscripts B and S refer to the bending and shear deformations. (Note the similarity with the Timoshenko beam theory for the inplane deformations of beams, where the first derivative of the displacement consists of two parts: $dv / dx = \chi + \gamma$, where the first term is the rotation of the cross section and the second is the transverse shear strain.) \hat{T}_ω is calculated from ϑ_S as

$$\hat{T}_\omega = S_{\omega\omega} \vartheta_S, \quad (7)$$

where $S_{\omega\omega}$ is the rotational shear stiffness. Eqns. 1, 3 and 4 are valid, however Eqn. 2 is replaced by

$$\Gamma = -\frac{d\vartheta_B}{dx}. \quad (8)$$

A theory, where the effect of shear deformation on restrained warping is taken into account was derived in [1] for open section composite beams. This paper can be considered as the generalization of [1] for closed section beams.

Table 1 summarizes the different beam theories available in the literature for torsion of closed section beams.

beam models	not isotropic	not orthotropic	restrained warping	shear in warping	arbitrary cross section
[7]	*		*		*
[6]	*	inaccurate for unsym. laminate			*
[10]	*	inaccurate for unsym. laminate	*		*
[3]	*	*			*
[12]			*	inaccurate	doubly sym. cross section
[14]	*	*	*	*	*
[13]			*	*	*
present [9]	*		*	*	*

Table 1: Comparison of composite beam theories.

Note that Wu and Sun's solution is rather complex and too tedious for design purposes, and Vlasov does not present cross sectional properties

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

We consider thin-walled closed section prismatic beams. The beam consists of flat segments (Fig. 2) designated by the subscript k ($k=1,2,\dots,K$, where K is the total number of the wall segments). The cross-section may be symmetrical or unsymmetrical and the layup of the wall is orthotropic. The beam may be subjected to distributed loads (shown in Fig. 2) or to concentrated loads. We wish to determine the displacements of the beam.

Fig. 2: Loads on a thin-walled beam

3. BASIC ASSUMPTIONS

Below we summarize the basic assumptions used in our beam model.

- (1) The material of the cross section behaves in a linearly elastic manner.
- (2) The effect of the displacements of the axis of the beam is not taken into account in the equilibrium equations.
- (3) The effect of change in geometry of the cross-section is not taken into account in the equilibrium equations.
- (4) The Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis is valid for each plate element.
- (5) The normal stresses in the contour directions are small compared to the axial stresses.
- (6) The form of the axial strain for pure torsion is

$$\epsilon_x^0 = \frac{du}{dx} - \omega \frac{d\vartheta_B}{dx}, \quad (9)$$

where u is the axial displacement, ϑ_B is the rate of twist from bending, and $\omega = \oint_0^s r ds$ is a section property called the sectorial area. The last term in Eqn. 9 represents an additional axial displacement of the cross section, called warping, proportional to the rate of twist from bending [8]. ϑ_B can be calculated as $\vartheta_B = d\psi / dx - \vartheta_S$, where ψ is the twist and ϑ_S is the rate of twist from shear.

The shear strain is supposed to be constant in the cross-section which is referred to as the first order shear theory. Coupling between normal and shearing effects are neglected.

4. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

We apply the first five assumptions given in the previous section. The sixth assumption will be used only in Section 5.

Using the governing equations of thin plates we can derive the differential equation of torsion for each wall segment (see the derivation in [9]).

$$-r_k \frac{\partial^2 \vartheta}{\partial x^2} + (\alpha_{66})_k \frac{\partial^2 q_k}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 q_k}{\partial \eta^2} = 0, \quad (10)$$

Fig. 3: Definition of u, s, r

where η is the circumferential coordinate, r is given in Fig. 3, ϑ is the rate of twist, $(\alpha_{66})_k$ and $(\alpha_{11})_k$ are the elements of the compliance matrix of the plate which can be calculated according to [2].

This second order differential equation is valid for every wall segment ($k=1, 2, \dots, K$). The following continuity conditions must be satisfied:

$$\begin{aligned}
-q_k \Big|_{\frac{b_k}{2}} &= q_{k+1} \Big|_{-\frac{b_{k+1}}{2}} & k = 1, 2, \dots, K \\
(\alpha_{11})_k \frac{\partial q_k}{\partial \eta} \Big|_{\frac{b_k}{2}} &= (\alpha_{11})_{k+1} \frac{\partial q_{k+1}}{\partial \eta} \Big|_{-\frac{b_{k+1}}{2}} & k = 1, 2, \dots, K
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

(Note that in the above equations $K+1$ must be replaced by 1, see Fig. 2.)

We solved this governing equations considering a simply supported beam (Fig. 4) subjected to a sinusoidal torque $t = \tilde{t} \sin \pi x / l$. At a simple support $\psi = 0$, $\psi' = 0$. We assume that the beam undergoes pure torsion. (Pure torsion occurs either when the cross section of the beam is doubly symmetrical or when the horizontal and vertical displacements (v , w) of the beam's axis are constrained.)

Fig. 4: Simply supported beam subjected to a sinusoidal torque

The solution of the problem is assumed to be in the form of the following functions

$$\vartheta = \tilde{\vartheta} \cos \frac{\pi x}{l}, \quad q_k = \tilde{q}_k(\eta) \cos \frac{\pi x}{l}, \tag{12}$$

where $\tilde{\vartheta}$ is a constant and \tilde{q}_k is a function of η only. Note that these functions satisfy the boundary conditions at $x=0$ and $x=l$.

The general solution of the differential equation system above is [9]

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\tilde{q}_k}{\tilde{\vartheta}} &= \frac{r_k}{(\alpha_{66})_k} + C_{1,k} e^{-\lambda_k \left(\frac{b_k}{2} + \eta \right)} + C_{2,k} e^{-\lambda_k \left(\frac{b_k}{2} - \eta \right)} \\
& k = 1, 2, \dots, K
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where

$$\lambda_k = \frac{\pi}{l} \sqrt{\frac{(\alpha_{66})_k}{(\alpha_{11})_k}}. \tag{14}$$

By substituting Eqn. 13 into Eqns. 11 we can obtain the $2 \times K$ unknown constants ($C_{1,k}, C_{2,k}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$) for a given $\tilde{\vartheta}$. From the shear flow the torque and the load can be calculated (for a given $\tilde{\vartheta}$) as

$$\hat{T} = \oint q r d\eta, \quad t = \frac{d\hat{T}}{dx}. \quad (15)$$

We emphasize that the shear flow (Eqn. 13) is the exact solution of the differential equation system, and hence, it can be used even in the case when the stiffnesses of the walls differ significantly.

When the loading conditions are not sinusoidal, we can write the Fourier series expansion of the load function. We obtain the solution of the problem by summing up the solutions of the element of the series.

5. BEAM THEORY

All the six assumptions of Section 3 are applied. In the following we give the governing equations in pure torsion. The case of bending-torsion coupling (unsymmetrical beams) can be found in [9].

For convenience we separate the shear flow q as

$$q = q_0 + q_\omega, \quad (16)$$

where q_0 is uniform around the circumference, and q_ω does not cause a twist. (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Shear flow $q = q_0 + q_\omega$

With Equations 1, 3, 4, 6, 7 and 8 we obtain the same equilibrium equations, strain-displacement relationship and stress-strain relationship as for open section beams [1], [9].

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{d}{dx} & -\frac{d}{dx} \\ & -1 \\ & & \frac{d}{dx} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \hat{T}_{sv} \\ \hat{T}_\omega \\ \hat{M}_\omega \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} t \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \vartheta \\ \vartheta_S \\ \Gamma \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dx} \\ \frac{d}{dx} & -1 \\ & -\frac{d}{dx} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Psi \\ \vartheta_B \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \hat{T}_{sv} \\ \hat{T}_\omega \\ \hat{M}_\omega \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \overline{GI}_t & & \\ & S_{\omega\omega} & \\ & & \overline{EI}_\omega \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \vartheta \\ \vartheta_S \\ \Gamma \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (19)$$

where \overline{GI}_t , $S_{\omega\omega}$ and \overline{EI}_ω are yet unknown stiffnesses.

To determine the stiffnesses \overline{GI}_t , $S_{\omega\omega}$ and \overline{EI}_ω of the beam, we write the strain energy of the beam as

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left(\int \left(\epsilon_\xi^0 N_\xi + \gamma_{\xi\eta}^0 q \right) d\eta \right) dx, \quad (20)$$

$$\epsilon_\xi^0 = \alpha_{11} N_\xi, \quad \gamma_{\xi\eta}^0 = \alpha_{66} q,$$

where q and N_ξ are determined for the beam subjected to sinusoidal load (Section 4).

On the other hand, the strain energy can be written with the cross sectional properties as

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left(\hat{T}_{sv} \vartheta + \hat{T}_\omega \vartheta_S + \hat{M}_\omega \Gamma \right) dx =$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left(\frac{\hat{T}_{sv}^2}{\overline{GI}_t} + \frac{\hat{T}_\omega^2}{S_{\omega\omega}} + \frac{\hat{M}_\omega^2}{\overline{EI}_\omega} \right) dx. \quad (21)$$

By comparing Eqns. 20 and 21 we obtain the stiffnesses [9] as

$$\overline{GI}_t = \frac{\left(\int q_0 r ds \right)^2}{\int \alpha_{66} q_0^2 d\eta} = \frac{4A^2}{\int \alpha_{66} d\eta}, \quad (22)$$

$$S_{\omega\omega} = \frac{\left(\int q_\omega r ds \right)^2}{\int \alpha_{66} q_\omega^2 d\eta}, \quad (23)$$

$$\overline{EI}_\omega = \frac{\left(\int q_\omega r ds \right)^2}{\int \alpha_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial \eta^2} \right)^2 d\eta}. \quad (24)$$

To determine $S_{\omega\omega}$ and \overline{EI}_ω the distribution of q_ω must be known. We may use the “exact” solution (see Eqn. 13). The shear flow q depends on the length l , consequently $S_{\omega\omega}$ and \overline{EI}_ω also depend on l . To derive stiffnesses which are independent of the length l we assumed that $l/b_k \ll 1$, where b_k is the width of the k th wall segment and used an approximate solution obtained via the Ritz method [9].

The expressions for a doubly symmetrical box section beam (notations are shown in Fig.7) are as follows:

$$\overline{GI}_t = \frac{2b_1^2 b_2^2}{X}, \quad (25)$$

$$S_{\omega\omega} = \frac{A^2}{2X^2} \frac{(\xi_2 - \xi_1)^2}{\xi_1 \xi_2 (1 + \kappa)}, \quad (26)$$

$$\overline{EI}_\omega = \frac{A^2}{24} (\xi_2 - \xi_1)^2 Z, \quad (27)$$

where

$$X = (\alpha_{66})_1 b_1 + (\alpha_{66})_2 b_2, \quad (28)$$

$$Z = \frac{b_1}{(\alpha_{11})_1} + \frac{b_2}{(\alpha_{11})_2}, \quad (29)$$

$$\xi_1 = \frac{b_1 (\alpha_{66})_1}{X}, \quad \xi_2 = 1 - \xi_1, \quad (30)$$

$$\eta_1 = \frac{b_1 / (\alpha_{11})_1}{Z}, \quad \eta_2 = 1 - \eta_1. \quad (31)$$

General cross-section beams are considered in [9].

In [9] several numerical examples were presented for transversely loaded beams which showed that the presented theory predicts accurately the torsion of the beam. In this paper we will apply the theory for the buckling of axially loaded columns and of transversely loaded beams.

6. APPLICATIONS FOR TORSIONAL AND LATERAL-TORSIONAL BUCKLING

In this section we demonstrate the utility of the presented theory through numerical examples. We consider a simply supported column subjected to a concentrated normal force at the end (Fig. 6a). The cross section of the beam is shown in Fig. 7a.

Fig. 6: Simply supported beam subjected to a normal force and to concentrated moments at the ends

Fig. 7: The cross sections in the numerical examples

T300/934	E_1 [MPa]	E_2 [MPa]	G_{12} [MPa]	ν_{12}
	148000	9650	4550	0.3

Table 2: Material properties of a graphite epoxy ply

The material properties are given in Table 2. The layup is orthotropic, and the fiber direction is parallel to the beam axis. For simplicity the dimensions are omitted below (the forces are given in N and the distances in mm).

With these properties the value of α_{11} and α_{66} for the flanges (subscript 1) and for the webs (subscript 2) are

$$\begin{aligned} (\alpha_{11})_1 &= 1.689 \times 10^{-6}, & (\alpha_{66})_1 &= 5.495 \times 10^{-5}, \\ (\alpha_{11})_2 &= 6.757 \times 10^{-6}, & (\alpha_{66})_2 &= 2.198 \times 10^{-4}. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

The stiffnesses of the beam are calculated by Eqns. 25, 26 and 27. With $b_1 = 50$ and $b_2 = 70$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{GI}_t &= 1.351 \times 10^9, & S_{\omega\omega} &= 1.048 \times 10^9, \\ \overline{EI}_\omega &= 9.909 \times 10^{12}. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

We calculated the bending and tensile stiffnesses according to the classical beam theories [2]

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{EA} &= 7.992 \times 10^7, & \overline{EI}_{yy} &= 8.114 \times 10^{10}, \\ \overline{EI}_{zz} &= 2.530 \times 10^{10}. \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

The governing equations of beams with open and closed cross sections are identical, hence the expressions presented in [1] for the buckling load of open section beams can be directly applied for closed section beams. Consequently the torsional critical load is

$$\frac{1}{N_{cr\omega}} = \frac{1}{N_{cr\omega}^B} + \frac{1}{i_\omega^2 S_{\omega\omega}}, \quad (35)$$

where

$$N_{cr\omega}^B = \frac{1}{i_\omega^2} \frac{\pi^2}{l^2} \overline{EI}_\omega, \quad i_\omega^2 = \frac{\overline{EI}_{zz} + \overline{EI}_{yy}}{EA}, \quad (36)$$

and

$$N_{cr\psi} = N_{cr\omega}^B + \frac{1}{i_\omega^2} \overline{GI}_t. \quad (37)$$

Fig. 8 shows $N_{cr\psi}$ as a function of the beam length. In this figure we included the results for the case when only \overline{GI}_t is considered. It can be seen that using the stiffnesses presented in this paper the solution is close to the ANSYS finite element solution. (Note that local buckling was excluded in the numerical calculation).

Fig. 8: Critical load of a simply supported column subjected to a normal force at the end (cross section is given in Fig. 7a)

Fig. 9: Critical load of a simply supported column subjected to a normal force at the end (cross section is given in Fig. 7b)

Fig. 10: Critical load of a simply supported beam subjected to concentrated moments at the ends (cross section is given in Fig. 7b)

We calculated the critical load also for the cross section in Fig. 7b. The values of α_{11} and α_{66} are

$$\begin{aligned} (\alpha_{11})_1 &= 1.351 \times 10^{-6}, & (\alpha_{66})_1 &= 4.396 \times 10^{-5}, \\ (\alpha_{11})_2 &= 6.757 \times 10^{-6}, & (\alpha_{66})_2 &= 2.198 \times 10^{-4}. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

The stiffnesses of the beam with $b_1 = 25$ and $b_2 = 125$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{GI}_t &= 6.836 \times 10^8, & S_{\omega\omega} &= 1.674 \times 10^9, \\ \overline{EI}_\omega &= 1.283 \times 10^{13}, & & \\ \overline{EA} &= 7.400 \times 10^7, & \overline{EI}_{yy} &= 1.9301 \times 10^{11}, \\ \overline{EI}_{zz} &= 7.721 \times 10^9. & & \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

Fig. 9 shows $N_{cr\psi}$ (calculated by the different methods) as a function of the beam length.

Let us consider a beam subjected to concentrated moments at the ends. The cross section is shown in Fig. 7b. This slender beam may buckle with a lateral-torsional buckling. We note again that the buckling load derived for open section beams [11] can directly be applied for closed section beams, hence we write:

$$M_{cr} = \sqrt{i_\omega^2 N_{crz} N_{cr\psi}}, \quad (40)$$

where

$$\frac{1}{N_{crz}} = \frac{1}{N_{crz}^B} + \frac{1}{S_{yy}}, \quad N_{crz}^B = \frac{\pi^2}{l^2} \overline{EI}_{zz}, \quad (41)$$

and S_{yy} is the lateral shear stiffness.

With these expressions we presented the buckling load as a function of the beam length in Fig. 10.

CONCLUSION

We presented a beam theory for thin-walled, closed section, orthotropic beams taking the restrained warping and the shear deformation into account. They play an important role when the stiffnesses of the walls (thickness and/or the layup) are significantly different from each other.

We gave numerical examples to demonstrate the accuracy of our beam model. The restrained warping and the shear deformation may affect the torsional stiffness of the beam, and consequently, the buckling load and the vibration characteristics.

REFERENCES

1. Kollár, L.P., "Flexural-torsional buckling of open section composite columns with shear deformation", *International Journal of Solids and Structures* Vol. 38, 2001, pp. 7525-7541.
2. Kollár, L.P. and Springer, G.S., "Mechanics of Composite Structures", Cambridge University Press, 2003
3. Kollár, L.P. and Pluzsik, A., "Analysis of Thin-Walled Composite Beams with Arbitrary Layup", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics & Composites* Vol. 21, 2002, pp. 1423-1465.
4. Kreyszig, E., "Advanced Engineering Mathematics", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1993
5. Kristek, V., "Theory of Box Girders" John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1979
6. Mansfield, E.H. and Sobey, A.J., "The Fiber Composite Helicopter Blade- Part 1: Stiffness Properties- Part 2: Prospectors for Aeroelastic Tailoring", *Aeronautical Quarterly* Vol. 30, 1979, pp. 413-449.
7. Massa, J.C. and Barbero, E.J., "A Strength of Materials Formulation for Thin Walled Composite Beams with Torsion", *Journal of Composite Materials* Vol. 32, 1998, pp. 1560-1594.
8. Megson, T.H.G., "Aircraft Structures for Engineering Students", Halsted Press, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1990
9. Pluzsik, A. and Kollár, L.P., "Torsion of Closed Section, Orthotropic, Thin-Walled Beams", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 2005, submitted for publication.
10. Rehfield, L.W., Atligan, A.R. and Hodges, D.H., "Nonclassical Behavior of Thin-Walled Composite Beams with Closed Cross Section", *American Helicopter Society National Technical Specialists' Meeting on Advanced Rotorcraft Structures*, Williamsburg, 1988
11. Sapkás, Á., and Kollár, L.P., "Lateral Torsional Buckling of Composite Beams with Shear Deformation", *International Journal of Solids and Structures* Vol. 39, 2002, pp. 2939-2963.
12. Urban, I.V., "Teoria Rascota Sterznevih Tonkostennih Konstrukcij", Gosudarstvennoe Transportnoe Zeleznodoroznoe Izdatelstvo, Moscow, 1955
13. Vlasov, V.Z., "Thin-walled elastic beams", Office of Technical Services. U.S. Department of Commerce, Wasington 25, DC, TT-61-11400, 1961
14. Wu, X. and Sun, C.T., "Simplified Theory for Composite Thin-Walled Beams". *AIAA Journal* Vol. 30, 1992, pp. 2945-2951.